

Investigating Academic Procrastination and its Implication for Academic Achievement in an Online Learning Setting

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Abstract:- The shift or transition to online learning brought by the intensified prevalence of COVID-19 pandemic has presented new challenges for the students including the increased opportunities for procrastination, which has been found to have detrimental impact on academic their academic achievement. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the association between academic procrastination and academic achievement among all second year Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students. A quantitative approach using descriptive-correlational technique was employed to achieve the objectives of the study. With the utilization of a well-established and reliable questionnaire, the researchers surveyed a total of 90 respondents using complete enumeration or census survey method. Furthermore, the collected data were analyzed through frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson product-moment correlation. The results revealed that the level of academic procrastination of the participants was moderate while their level of academic achievement was very good. However, upon conducting the correlation test, there was no significant association between academic procrastination and academic achievement. This finding suggests that in this present study, students' academic achievement is not influenced by their tendency to procrastinate.

Keywords:- Facebook Addiction; Loneliness; COVID-19; Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development and improvement of students' academic achievement is the most vital indicator of all colleges' and universities' progress [1]. Academic achievement is an important component and indicator of student success. It has a huge impact on education, especially by identifying key practical methods to assess the students' learning progress [2]. At present, improving the academic achievement of the student is quite challenging, especially amidst the COVID -19 pandemic. Due to the lockdown

brought on by the pandemic, schools and universities have constructed alternative teaching-learning processes to continue academic activities without physical meetups [3]. The face-to-face classes changed drastically to remote settings, particularly in online or virtual learning modes, with the help of the internet and communication technologies [4]. However, several students complained about the adjustment and readiness of the online learning setup, which provoked their bad attitude and behavioral problems toward academic commitments, such as laziness, disengagement, being uninterested, and unmotivated resulting in low academic achievement [5] and dropouts [6].

One of the concerned student behavioral problem is tendency to procrastinate. In the body of knowledge, the term procrastination refers to a behavioral action or disposition of a person who intentionally delays their task to the extent of not meeting the deadlines and the postponement of task completions that leads to adverse consequences and unfavorable outcomes [7][8]. Procrastination typically happens when a task is unduly put off, and people become tremendously disturbed and troubled when they begin to think or work on it. A study posited that there are different varieties of procrastination, such as academic procrastination, neurotic procrastination, compulsive procrastination, and decisional procrastination [7]. Among these types of procrastination, academic procrastination was widely studied by different experts around the globe [9][10].

Academic procrastination is considered a specific type of behavioral procrastination. It refers to the tendency to voluntarily delay an intended course of study-related action despite the inevitable negative consequences of such a delay [11]. This type of procrastination affects over 70% of college students and is reportedly associated with unsatisfactory academic performance and higher levels of stress and anxiety [12][13]. It is often conceptualized as a behavioral pattern to avoid difficult or anxiety-evoking tasks [14], a motivational issue that reflects individual differences in general values [15], a time management problem [16] or a metacognitive

self-regulation failure [17]. This maladaptive behavior is associated with a range of personal characteristics such as perfectionism, fear of failure, low self-efficacy, low self-regulation, and behavioral rigidity, as well as motivational aspects such as goal orientation and situational aspects such as class climate and task difficulty [18].

The consequences of procrastination often include negative affective, mental, and behavioral aspects such as unstable health, poor self-image, poor social impression, stress, and professional inconsistency [19]. Several researchers have found that students' academic procrastination is strongly associated with dysfunctional learning outcomes such as low academic performance, low quality of academic work, lack of knowledge, time pressure, dropout, and lengthened course of study [20][21]. Michinov, Brunot, Le Bohec, Juhel, and Delaval [22], who studied academic procrastination in online environments, found that high-level academic procrastinators were less successful online learners than low-level procrastinators and that high-level procrastinators found it more difficult to (re)start studying online while not on campus. Klassen, Tze, and Hannok [23] found that high-level procrastinators reported lower GPAs, expected and received lower class grades, spent more hours procrastinating each day, took longer to begin important assignments, and expressed less confidence that they were capable of regulating their learning. Although high-level procrastinators fared more poorly than low-level procrastinators, they did experience a degree of success in the university setting [16][17][18].

Arguments on whether procrastination affects students' performance in school and vice-versa or not have become the central theme of researchers today, adding to the factors of a 'lazy' attitude and the difficulties encountered in current learning modalities. In the study of Tiboron et al. [24], procrastination is defined as a set of virtues innate in oneself, so it cannot be avoided. They added that external factors, such as lack of motivation and loss of interest, affect oneself. It can also be physiological, attributed to poor health and diet. Procrastination could also result from a lack of academic goals and failure in the past [25]. They expounded that a tightly hectic schedule causes stress, poor internet connectivity, discouragement, and inconvenience, which contribute to procrastinating. Most tendencies of procrastinating are found among college students, as revealed in the studies of Asio [10], Mandap [26], Anuddin [27], and Morales [28] in which each has found that procrastinating is a positive or negative influence on academic achievement.

Karmen et al. [29] highlighted the association between procrastination, academic attitude, and academic performance. In this case, procrastination has two domains: intentional and passive. As the correlation of the test was done, the results showed that both domains of procrastination were negatively associated with academic performance. They suggest that students who procrastinate more passively showed lower academic results.

On the other hand, the study of Asio [10] testified to the results mentioned above. The study aimed to discover the relationship between academic procrastination and the academic performance of freshmen students. The research results revealed that academic procrastination is negatively associated with students' grade point average (GPA). They further suggested that when students procrastinate, they lack self-monitoring, goal setting, and self-regulated learning, possibly routed to negative academic achievement.

However, some studies contradicted the relationship between procrastination and academic achievement. For example, the study of Janseen [30] investigated the relationship between procrastination and academic achievement among undergraduate students. Unexpectedly, their result showed that there is no link between the variables.

Finally, the finding is likewise consistent with the work of Johal [31] who discovered an insignificant association between procrastination and academic achievement. These authors explained that procrastination might not be a predictor of academic achievement. The author further suggested that in the context of the study, academic achievement does not rely on procrastination but possibly on other factors such as parental influence, financial struggle, motivation, and others.

In the Philippines, this popular culture, such as *mañana*, cramming, and bad mannerism, have been increasingly observed during remote learning, which created hostile effects on modular distance or online learning and the time management of students [5]. Notably, these issues were manifested among BEED 2 students of San Agustin Institute of Technology in Valencia City, Bukidnon. These issues promote a decrease in their scholastic ratings and result in failing grades. That is why, the researchers investigated the positive relationship between procrastinating and students' academic achievement.

While there were several studies related to procrastination and academic achievement in previous literature, no studies have been conducted as of the COVID-19 pandemic, especially among students in Valencia City, Bukidnon. Therefore, the researchers attempted to do one.

II. METHODS

A. Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative approach with a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement among BEED 2 students at the San Agustin Institute of Technology. This research design involves collecting numerical data through surveys and analyzing them using statistical methods to identify patterns and correlations between variables [3] [32]. Descriptive research was used to describe the level of academic procrastination and academic achievement of the respondents while

correlation was employed to examine the relationship between the two (2) variables.

B. Research Local and Participants

The study was conducted at San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT), Fr. Manlio Caroselli S.J. St., Poblacion, Valencia City, Bukidnon. The school is a private Catholic institution founded by an Italian missionary priest, Fr. Manlio Caroselli S.J., in 1960. The school has elementary, high school, and college departments. The study's sample consisted of second-year BEED students who were enrolled at San Agustin Institute of Technology. As reported by the SAIT Registrar, the total population of the BEED students is 90, included in the final dataset. The sampling procedure employed in this study was complete enumeration or cen sus survey method, which involves gathering data from the entire population rather than selecting a sample. In other words, all BEED students had the opportunity to participate in the study, following the principles outlined by the OECD (2008).

C. Research Instruments

The questionnaire used in this study was adapted from the study of Asio [10] entitled, *"The Relationship between Academic Procrastination and Academic Performance of Freshmen Students from a Teacher Education Institution."* This questionnaire aims to measure the students' academic procrastination level. Meanwhile, the academic achievement is the grade weighted average (GWA) of the respondents taken from the Registrar's office. Following the proposal defense, the questionnaire underwent validation and reliability testing. The findings indicated that the questionnaire was highly reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .949. This high reliability score suggests that the questionnaire consistently measures the intended constructs accurately, and the data collected from it, is dependable.

D. Ethical Consideration

The researchers in this study always prioritized respect for the respondents and wholeheartedly accepted it if respondents declined to answer the survey. The privacy and confidentiality of the respondents' personal information were observed by the researchers throughout the study. Before the research was conducted, the researchers sought permission from the Dean of College and the Head of the education program, as well as the respondents' consent. To ensure that the respondents fully understood the study's objectives and potential risks, the researchers provided them with detailed information. Respondents who declined to participate in the study were not forced to do so.

Therefore, all respondents who answered the questionnaires fully participated voluntarily in the study. The researchers strictly observed ethical protocols in the conduct of the research to ensure that the participants' rights were respected. The researchers understand and respect the respondents' decisions, including those who chose not to participate in the study. Overall, the researchers' commitment to ethical standards and respect for the respondents' rights helped to ensure the credibility and validity of the study's findings. The researchers used plagiarism detection software on the paper to ensure its authenticity. Above all, in order to create the best ethically-controlled study possible, the researchers applied all ethical guidelines during the conduct of research.

III. RESULTS

A. Level of Academic Procrastination

Table 1 presents the academic procrastination of the respondents with an overall mean of 3.25 (SD=0.65), described as "neutral," and interpreted as "moderate." It must be noted that the item statement, *"When working on schoolwork, I usually get distracted by other things,"* obtained the highest mean of 3.75 (SD=1.00), described as "agree," and interpreted as "high." Meanwhile, the item statement, *"I know I should work on schoolwork, but I just do not do it,"* got the lowest mean of 3.03 (SD=1.16), described as "neutral," and interpreted as "moderate."

Table 1: Level of Academic Procrastination

	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	When working on schoolwork, I usually get distracted by other things.	3.75	1.00	High
2.	I concentrate on schoolwork instead of other distractions.	3.72	0.80	High
3.	I get distracted by other more fun things when I am supposed to work on schoolwork.	3.63	1.02	High
4.	I waste a lot of time on unimportant things.	3.62	1.12	High
5.	I read the textbook and look over notes before coming to class and listen to a lecture or discussion with my teacher.	3.58	0.87	High
6.	I allocate time so I do not have to "cram" at the end of the semester.	3.52	0.85	High
7.	I only study the night before exams.	3.50	1.00	High
8.	I feel prepared well in advance for most tests.	3.40	0.85	Moderate
9.	"Cramming" and last-minute studying is the best way that I study for a big test.	3.40	1.01	Moderate
10.	I tend to put off things for the next day.	3.40	0.91	Moderate
11.	If an assignment is due at midnight, I will work on it until 11:59.	3.37	0.94	Moderate
12.	I cannot focus on schoolwork or projects for more than an hour until I get distracted.	3.35	0.99	Moderate
13.	I have found myself waiting until the day before to start a big project.	3.32	0.83	Moderate
14.	Tests are meant to be studied for just the night before.	3.32	1.05	Moderate
15.	I put off projects until the last minute.	3.27	1.07	Moderate
16.	If I do not understand something, I will usually wait until the night before a test to figure it out.	3.27	0.95	Moderate
17.	My attention span for schoolwork is very short.	3.22	0.99	Moderate
18.	I find myself talking to friends or family instead of working on schoolwork.	3.22	0.88	Moderate
19.	When given an assignment, I usually put it away and forget about it until it is almost due.	3.18	1.05	Moderate
20.	I frequently find myself putting important deadlines off.	3.18	0.89	Moderate
21.	On the weekends, I make plans to do homework and projects, but I get distracted and hang out with friends.	3.15	0.94	Moderate
22.	Friends usually distract me from schoolwork.	3.13	1.02	Moderate
23.	I do not spend much time studying school material until the end of the semester.	3.12	0.99	Moderate
24.	I do not usually allocate time to review and proofread my work.	3.05	0.85	Moderate
25.	I know I should work on schoolwork, but I just do not do it.	3.03	1.16	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.35	0.65	Moderate

B. Level Academic Achievement

Table 2 presents the level of academic achievement of BEED 2 students of San Agustin Institute of Technology with an overall mean of 1.46 (SD=0.26), described as "very good." Furthermore, 35 or 58.3 % of the students have a grade of 1.1 to 1.5, described as "very good." On the other hand, 23 or 38.3 % of the students attain a grade of 1.6 to 2.0, which means "good." Lastly, the result reveals that none of the students got excellent or failing grade.

Table 2: Level of Academic Achievement

Grade Range	Frequency	Percent	Description
1.0	0	0.0	Excellent
1.1-1.5	35	58.3	Very Good
1.6-2.0	23	38.3	Good
2.1-2.5	2	3.3	Satisfactory
2.6-3.0	0	0.0	Passing
3.1-3.5	-	-	Failure
Total	60	100.0	
	Mean = 1.46	SD = 0.26	Very Good

C. Correlation Analysis Academic Procrastination and Academic Achievement.

Table 3 presents the correlation analysis between the independent and dependent variables of the study. The result revealed that there was no significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement as indicated by $r=0.204$ and $p=0.117$. The finding means that academic procrastination has nothing to do with academic achievement of the students. **Therefore, the null hypothesis that states, "There is no significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement of BEED 2 students," is accepted.**

Table 3: Correlation Analysis between Academic Procrastination and Academic Achievement

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement		
	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Academic Procrastination	0.204	0.117	Not Significant

IV. DISCUSSION AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATION

A. Academic Procrastination

The findings of the study indicate that the respondents perceived a moderate level of academic procrastination. Specifically, the results revealed that most of the respondents reported experiencing difficulties in concentration and were easily distracted by engaging in leisure activities such as going out with friends, attending irrelevant events, and gaming. As a consequence, some of the respondents almost forgot about the deadlines of their academic requirements. The study also revealed that many of the respondents perceived that academic requirements were still too far in the future, leading them to believe that they still had ample time to complete their work. As a result, they tended to procrastinate, leading to a tendency to forget about the deadlines set. Furthermore, the results showed that many respondents agreed that they sometimes experienced "cramming" due to wasting a lot of time on unnecessary things.

Thus, these perceived attitudes and behaviors concurred with the proposition of several authors [7][8][9][10] who posited that students with moderate to a high level of procrastination are related to a lack of self-regulation, time management problems, and behavioral problem such as failure in completing their task efficiently, frequent cramming and avoiding difficult or anxiety-evoking tasks.

B. Academic Achievement.

The finding reveals that the academic achievement level of the second-year BEED students at San Augustin Institute of Technology is good. Most students displayed very good academic performance, demonstrated strong abilities, perspectives, perseverance, diligence, and a goal of achieving high grades. These tools are important in having good performances in their studies which are agreed by experts [33][34]. Academic achievement is the level of learning and knowledge gained by the students, which is assessed through the marks/score of a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to achieve over a specific period of time. Also, the ability of students to get high academic scores is due to their focus on the teaching environment, interest, and motivation. Arshad, Zaidi, and Mahmood [35] also indicated that the academic score measures the outcome of education. The definitions provided by the authors show that the meaning of academic grade is the result or measure of the students' ability and success in various academic subjects.

C. Significant Relationship between Academic Procrastination and Academic Achievement

The correlation analysis revealed that academic procrastination has no significant relationship with the students' academic achievement. **Therefore, the null hypothesis that states, "There is no significant relationship between academic procrastination and students' academic achievement," is accepted.** This finding contrasts with the results of a previous study by Asio

[10], which suggests that academic procrastination can have a negative impact on students' academic performance. It is important to note, however, that the current study's sample prevalence assessment of this incident revealed some significant results in other areas. The present result agrees with the findings of Janseen [30], who discovered an insignificant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement among undergraduate students. The finding likewise concurs with the result of Johal [31], who likewise testified to the existence of an insignificant association between procrastination and academic achievement. These authors explain that procrastination may not link to academic achievement since academic achievement is multifaceted that cannot be measured just by one factor. Both authors further suggested that in the context of the study, academic achievement is not dependent on the students' procrastination behavior but possibly on some other factors such as parental influence, financial struggle, motivation, and others.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The present study showed that although many students experienced moderate levels of academic procrastination, they were still able to perform very well in their studies and achieve good grades. Furthermore, the study found no significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement, indicating that academic procrastination may not necessarily impact students' academic achievement.

Thus, the result of the study invalidates the Attribution Theory, as developed by Weiner in 1985 [36]. This theory is a psychological framework that explores how individuals interpret and explain the causes of events, behaviors, and outcomes. It focuses on how people attribute success or failure to specific factors, which can influence their motivation, emotions, and subsequent behavior. In the context of the relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement, attribution theory can shed light on how individuals explain their procrastination tendencies and how it affects their academic achievement. The theory suggests that when students attribute success, which can be related to academic achievement, such as believing they have control over their outcomes (e.g., time management and goal setting) and are more motivated to engage in tasks promptly (e.g., actively participate in class discussions, take on challenging assignments, persist in the face of difficulties, and exhibit a proactive approach to their studies), they exhibit lower level of procrastination. Similarly, students who attribute failures, such as lack of ability or effort, experience feelings of incompetence or helplessness and having difficulties to succeed specific task or situation may fostering procrastination behavior. However, in this study, the results showed that there is no significant association between the academic procrastination and academic achievement among BEED students. Therefore, the study does not support the theory.

As for recommendation, the researchers would like to address the issue of academic procrastination, the following recommendations are suggested:

School administrators may support students in managing their academic time and monitor their academic progress. This can be done by providing workshops on time management skills and offering resources such as automated reminders to help students stay on track.

Teachers may analyze the situation and identify the factors that may be contributing to students' procrastination behavior. Then, they can implement appropriate interventions such as intermediate deadlines, self-regulation, and personalized feedback to help students overcome their procrastination habits.

Parents may be informed about the possible impact of poor time management on their children's academic performance. They can monitor their children's activities and offer guidance on how to manage their time effectively.

Students may be encouraged to develop time management skills, such as prioritization and planning, to prevent academic procrastination and maintain their motivation for productive reasons.

Future researchers may expand on this study by incorporating additional factors that may impact academic achievement and conducting comparative studies across different settings and schools

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